

Article

The first species of the ant genus *Temnothorax* Mayr, 1861 (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) described from the Philippines

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Abstract

A new species of the myrmicine ant genus *Temnothorax* Mayr, 1861 is described from Mt. Isarog Natural Park, Bicol Peninsula, Luzon Island, Philippines. *Temnothorax melanieae* n. sp. is the first species described from the Philippines. It is distinguished by the 11-segmented antennae with 3-segmented club, longitudinally gently convex clypeus with a median carina, absent metanotal groove, and an acutely cuneiform petiole. This species represents a significant eastward extension of the geographical range of this mostly Holarctic genus.

Key words: Holarctic distribution, leaf litter sampling, new species, range extension, transect survey

Introduction

The myrmicine ant genus *Temnothorax* Mayr, 1861 is a large genus of 503 valid species and 33 valid subspecies (Bolton 2025), predominantly distributed in the Holarctic realm, from Japan (Terayama and Onoyama 1999), Europe (Radchenko 2004), Vietnam (Eguchi et al. 2011), northern Africa (Prebus 2015), the New World (Prebus 2021), and China (Qian and Xu 2024; and Wei et al. 2024).

The genus has been the subject of intense interest and research in recent years. Prebus (2015) revised the Afrotropical species of the genus, describing four new species. Then Prebus (2021) published a key to the Neotropical clades of *Temnothorax* and revised the *salvini* clade, recognizing 63 species of which 35 species were new to science.

Within Asia, the genus has also been treated with much interest. Terayama and Onoyama (1999) revised the Japanese species of *Temnothorax* (then known under the genus *Leptothorax* Mayr, 1855). Zhou et al. (2010) described eight new species and reported three new distributional records from China. From Vietnam, Eguchi et al. (2011) listed two species which remain undescribed to this date. Bharti et al. (2012) described three new species and published a key to the Indian species of *Temnothorax*, which they updated and revised in 2016 (Bharti et al. 2016). Sharaf et al. (2017) revised the Arabian *Temnothorax* fauna, recognizing three species including one new species, one new taxonomic combination, and a previously described species. Sharaf et al. (2019) used micro-CT tomography to describe a new Arabian species. Sharaf and Aldawood (2019) described one new species and published a revised key to the five known Arabian species. Yusupov et al. (2020a) described two new species and provided a key to the species of Pakistan. Yusupov et al. (2020b) described a new species and provided a key to the Himalayan species from India. Hamer and Guénard (2023) described two new species from Hong Kong. Subedi et al. (2023) described three new species and provided a key to the known species in Nepal. Qian and Xu (2024) described 28 new species from China and provided a key to the known Chinese species. Subsequently, Wei et al. (2024) described a new bi-colored species, also from China.

The presence of the genus in the Philippines was first reported by General et al. (2020) from a transect survey in the Mt. Isarog Natural Park. This contribution describes that unique specimen and presents the first taxonomic description of a *Temnothorax* species from the Philippines.

Materials and methods

The unique specimen was collected by diurnal leaf litter sifting during a transect study in Mt. Isarog Natural Park in the Bicol Peninsula, Luzon Island, Philippines (Fig.1) last 2019 (General et al. 2020), with the appropriate collecting permit by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources. Morphological observations and measurements were made using Nikon SMZ800N equipped with an ocular micrometer. A Sony Exmor CMOS Sensor camera captured digital images that were processed with ToupLite for macOS ver.2.1 and stacked with Focus Stacker.

Figure 1. Approximate location of Mt. Isarog Natural Park (yellow dot), in the Bicol Peninsula of Luzon Island, Philippines.

The following measurements and indices were taken and computed, following Qian and Xu (2024):

HL: Head Length, the maximum length of the head from the anterior clypeal margin to the midpoint of a line drawn across the occipital margin, measured in full-face view.

HW: Head Width, the maximum width of the head, measured in full-face view.

SL: Scape Length, the maximum length of the antennal scape excluding the basal neck and condyle.

EL: Eye Length, the maximum length of compound eye, measured in oblique view.

PW: Pronotal Width, the maximum width of pronotum, measured in dorsal view.

WL: Weber's Length, the diagonal distance between the point at which the pronotum meets the cervical shield and the posterior margin of the propodeal lobe, measured in lateral view.

PetL: Petiole Length, the length of the petiole from the anterior articulation to the posterior articulation, measured in lateral view.

PetH: Petiole Height, vertical distance from apex of subpetiolar process to an imaginary line intersecting the apex of the petiolar node, measured in lateral view.

CI: Cephalic Index, HW/HL x 100

SI: Scape Index, SL/HW x 100

Depository

PNM National Museum of Natural History, National Museum of the Philippines

Taxonomy

Class Insecta Linnaeus, 1758

Order Hymenoptera Linnaeus, 1758

Family Formicidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Myrmicinae Lepeletier de Saint-Fargeau, 1835

Genus *Temnothorax* Mayr, 1861

***Temnothorax melanieae* n. sp.** (Figs. 2-5)

<https://zoobank.org/1E8932EF-674D-4365-B027-ACBFA4E1E179>

Material examined. Unique Holotype: PHILIPPINES, Luzon Island, Camarines Sur Province, Municipality of Pili, Barangay (=Village) Del Rosario, Mt. Isarog Natural Park, 600 masl, ex. transect study diurnal leaf litter sifting, 23.ii.2019, leg. D.E.M. General, P.A.C. Buenavente, and L.J.V. Rodriguez. Deposited in PNM (PNM 18870).

Measurements (mm): HL 0.55, HW 0.54, SL 0.41, EL 0.14, PW 0.31, WL 0.63, PetL 0.23, PetH 0.20, CI 116, SI 87.

Diagnosis. Mandibles with 5 teeth, decreasing in size from apex to base; mandibles weakly striate; anterior clypeal margin convex; clypeus longitudinally gently convex and with a median carina; head punctate with weak longitudinal striation; lateral margins of head slightly convex, widest at position of the eyes; eyes exceed the lateral margin of head; posterior margin of head entire; antenna 11-segmented with 3-segmented club; antennal scape just reaching posterior margin of head, when laid back; first funicular segment longer than next three succeeding segments; segments 2-6 wider than long; segment 7 about as long as wide; terminal segment much longer than previous two segments combined; mesosoma slightly convex or flat; metanotal groove absent; propodeal spine curving posteriorly; petiole acutely cuneiform, with no dorsal face; postpetiole convex dorsally.

Description

Structures. In **full face view**, head subrectangular, longer than broad (CI 116), with weakly convex sides and occipital margin, rounded occipital corners. Clypeus widely inserted between antennal lobes; anterior margin convex and sinuate laterally; median clypeal carina present. Mandible broadly triangular, masticatory margin with five teeth, decreasing in size from apex to base. Frontal carinae weakly developed, extending from the antennal insertions to midlength of eye; frontal lobes present. Antenna with 11 segments terminating in a 3-segmented club, first funicular segment longer than next three succeeding segments, segments 2-6 wider than long; segment 7 about as long as wide, terminal segment much longer than previous two segments combined. Scape of medium length (SI 87), just reaching posterior corners of head. Eye convex; located at midlength of head and extending beyond lateral margin of head. In lateral view, eyes composed of 11-12 ommatidia across longest axis. In dorsal view, occipital carina well-developed.

In **dorsal view**, mesosoma widest at midlength of pronotum; humeri rounded; mesosomal margin posterior to pronotum subparallel, but widening slightly at the level of the propodeal lobes. Promesonotal suture absent dorsally but present laterally. Metanotal groove absent. In lateral view, mesosoma weakly convex or flat. Propodeal spiracle circular, directed lateroposteriorly. Propodeal lobe round. Propodeal spines well-developed, long, and slightly curving downward starting at midlength; spines longer than the distance between their bases, spine divergent from base then becoming subparallel at terminal 1/4, in dorsal view. In lateral view, propodeal declivity weakly concave.

In **lateral view**, petiole acutely cuneiform, with no dorsal face. Postpetiole short and convex. In dorsal view, postpetiole subtrapezoidal; distinctly wider than petiole. First gastral tergite long; anterolateral corners roundly angled.

Pilosity. In full face view, mandible dorsum with subdecumbent pilosity and posterior margin of head with a few erect setae; in lateral view, a pair of short blunt erect setae arise from median clypeus and another pair at frons. Antennal scape and funicular segments with fine subdecumbent pubescence. In lateral view, gaster with sparse erect setae.

Sculpture. In full face view, dorsum of head finely punctate with a smooth region medially on frons; fine longitudinal carinae behind frons; mandibles weakly striate over ground punctulation. Mesosoma dorsally and laterally rugulose, forming faint longitudinal ridges. Dorsum of petiole and postpetiole punctulate. Gaster smooth.

Colour. Head and body concolorous orange-yellow. Setae yellowish white.

Figures 2-5. *Temnothorax melanieae* n. sp. (2) Head in full-face view. (3) Lateral view. (4) Dorsal view. (5) Labels.

Ecology. This species was collected during diurnal leaf litter sifting and Winkler extraction. The missing right middle and hind legs and left antenna suggest that this specimen was a prey item of other ants that were collected at the same time. Among the possible predators concurrently collected then are:

Carebara "sp3", *Pheidole hortensis* Forel, 1913, *Pheidole kikutai* Eguchi, 2001, and *Sylophopsis* "sp2" (General et al. 2020).

Etymology. This species is lovingly dedicated to my eldest daughter, Melanie Jane R. General.

Comparative Notes. *Temnothorax melanieae* n. sp., with 11-segmented antenna, a rare condition in the genus, drops out in couplet 5 of the key of Qian and Xu (2024), where the only other species with 11-segmented antenna is *T. koreanus* (Teranishi, 1940) which is chocolate brown and has a dorsolaterally angulate pronotum in dorsal view and a petiole with a rounded dorsum. *Temnothorax melanieae* n. sp., possessing both fine punctation and fine longitudinal rugulae, fails at couplet 15 of the original key of Zhou et al. (2010) and at couplet 15c of the part of the key modified by Hamer et al. (2023).

Discussion

This taxonomic study and description of the first species of *Temnothorax* confirms the initial record of the genus by General et al. (2020) who reported it as "*Temnothorax* sp1". The discovery of *T. melanieae* n. sp. represents a significant eastward extension of the geographic range of the genus. The next nearest distribution of *Temnothorax* ants is Vietnam, where Eguchi et al. (2011) found two species that remain undescribed. Since Luzon Island is an oceanic island, the process by which *Temnothorax* ants arrived is unknown.

Temnothorax melanieae n. sp. also represents the 106th ant genus known in the Philippines (DEMG, in prep.), comparing favorably with Australia (111 genera) and Borneo (109 genera) (AntWiki 2025b).

Many islands, mountains, and other natural areas in the Philippines await exploration for ant diversity. It is quite likely that many more new species and even new genus distributional records will be discovered there.

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